

Methoxymethylation and benzyloxymethylation of aryl bromides

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The methoxymethylation and benzyloxymethylation of aryl bromides methodology was reported here. The transition metal free, high yielding one pot procedure will be useful for synthetic community.

Keywords: MOM-Cl, BOM-Cl, aryl bromide, organolithium, alkoxyalkylation.

Introduction

The methoxymethyl (MOM) and benzyloxymethyl (BOM) moieties are frequently used protecting group for protection of alcohols, thiols and carboxylic acids¹. The halogen-carbon bond in alpha-halo ethers is easily cleaved heterolytically, because the adjacent oxygen can stabilize the carbocation formed and it can be explained by stabilization of one of the filled non-bonding orbitals on the oxygen atom by overlap with an unfilled antibonding orbitals between carbon and chlorine (Scheme 1). Indeed Olah *et al.* reported that the carbenium ion from methoxymethyl chloride can be isolated as its fluoroantimonate salt². The facile cleavage of the carbon-halogen bond in alpha-haloethers results in high reactivity under both SN1 and SN2 conditions³. The reactivity patterns of α -haloethers are follow the similar order as observed in case of alkyl halides, i.e. α -iodo > α -bromo > α -chloro > α -fluoro. Generally, α -monohalo ethers have been used as electrophilic alkoxyalkylating agents. In recent years, however, new procedures for the transformation of α -monohalo ethers into other useful intermediates have appeared⁴⁻¹⁰.

Scheme 1

Experimental

General procedure:

n-BuLi (1.2 mmol) was added to a THF (6 ml) solution of aryl bromide (1 mmol) at -78°C . After stirring for 1 h at same

temperature, a THF solution of MOM-Cl or BOM-Cl (1.1 mmol in 4 ml dry THF) was added dropwise to it. Stirring was continued for another 1 h at same temperature and slowly warmed to 0°C over another 1 h and quenched with saturated aqueous ammonium chloride solution. The organic layer was separated and aqueous layer was extracted with diethyl ether. The combined organic layer was dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated. Column chromatographic purification gave the desired product.

1-(4-(Methoxymethyl)phenyl)-3-methyleneazetidine (2):

Following general procedure, 76% yield, gummy liquid, ^1H NMR (CD_2Cl_2 , 400 MHz): δ 7.17 (d, J 8.44 Hz, 2H), 6.45 (d, J 8.44 Hz, 2H), 5.00 (t, J 2.34 Hz, 2H), 4.44 (dd, J 2.3 Hz, 2.28 Hz, 4H), 4.31 (s, 2H), 3.30 (s, 3H); ^{13}C NMR (CD_2Cl_2 , 100 MHz): δ 150.9, 139.7, 129.0, 127.2, 111.5, 105.6, 74.4, 60.9, 57.2; HRMS: (CI-MS): m/z for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}$ (M+H)⁺ Calcd. 190.1232, Found 190.1235.

4-(3-Methyleneazetidin-1-yl)benzoic acid (7):

To a stirred solution of compound **1** (448 mg, 2 mmol) in a mixture of THF (12 ml) and n-hexane (12 ml) at -78°C , n-BuLi (1.6 M) (1.5 ml, 2.4 mmol) was added dropwise over 15 min. After 1 h at -78°C , the mixture was poured onto an excess of freshly crushed dry ice. Water (5.0 ml) was added to it. The aqueous phase was washed with diethyl ether (2 \times 30 ml), acidified to pH 1 by aqueous HCl and extracted with dichloromethane (4 \times 30 ml). The organic (DCM) layer was dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated to obtain the crude carboxylic acid **7** (205 mg, 54%) and this was used for the next step without purification.

(4-(3-Methyleneazetidin-1-yl)phenyl)methanol (8):

To a stirred suspension of lithium aluminum hydride (1.2 g, 9 mmol) in dry THF (15 ml) under argon atmosphere, compound **7** (567 mg, 3 mmol) in dry THF (10 ml) was added dropwise at 0°C. The mixture was heated under reflux, with vigorous stirring, for 1.5 h. After cooling, aqueous NH₄Cl solution was added, and it was extracted with dichloromethane. The organic layers were combined, dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered, and concentrated under vacuum. After purification by flash chromatography (ethyl acetate/petroleum ether), colorless oil **8** (384 mg, 73%) was obtained.

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.22–7.20 (m, 2H), 6.44 (d, *J* 8.5 Hz, 2H), 4.98 (d, *J* 2.36 Hz, 2H), 4.54 (s, 2H), 4.29 (m, 4H); HRMS: (CI-MS): *m/z* for C₁₁H₁₄NO (M+H)⁺ Calcd. 176.1075, Found 176.1079.

N-(2-(Iodomethyl)allyl)-4-(methoxymethyl)-N-methylaniline (9):

To a stirred suspension of sodium hydride (72 mg, 3 mmol) in dry THF (15 ml) under argon atmosphere, compound **8** (350 mg, 2 mmol) in dry THF (6 ml) was added dropwise at 0°C. The mixture was heated under reflux, with vigorous stirring, for 1.5 h. After cooling, aqueous NH₄Cl solution was added, and it was extracted with dichloromethane. The organic layers were combined, dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered, and concentrated under vacuum. After purification by flash chromatography (ethyl acetate/petroleum ether), colorless oil **9** (717 mg, 78%) was obtained.

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.17 (d, *J* 8.76 Hz, 2H), 6.70 (d, *J* 8.7 Hz, 2H), 5.33 (d, *J* 0.84 Hz, 1H), 5.00 (d, *J* 1.08 Hz, 1H), 4.32 (s, 2H), 4.05 (s, 2H), 3.90 (s, 2H), 3.31 (s, 3H), 2.95 (s, 3H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz): δ 149.4, 142.9, 129.6, 126.3, 114.9, 112.3, 74.8, 57.8, 56.3, 38.7; HRMS: (CI-MS): *m/z* for C₁₃H₁₉INO (M+H)⁺ Calcd. 332.0511, Found: 332.0507.

Results and discussion

In conjunction with a project underway in our laboratory, we faced the problem of synthesizing, in quantity, the methoxymethyl substituted azitidine **2** from the corresponding bromo compound **1** (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Generally, for the conversion of aryl bromides to corresponding methoxymethyl ether can be obtainable via three steps, first the lithiation of aromatic compound through the reaction of aromatic bromides with *n*-BuLi and followed by carboxylation of *in situ* generated aryl lithium. Secondly, the reduction of carboxylic acids to corresponding alcohols and finally methylation of alcohol gave the desired methoxymethylated aryl derivatives (Scheme 3).

Accordingly, compound **1** was subjected to react with *n*-BuLi at -78°C, the metal halogen exchange produce the aryl lithium species which was react with carbondioxide (dry ice) and gave the corresponding carboxylic acid **7** in moderate yield (Scheme 4). The LiAlH₄ reduction of acid **7** under refluxing condition in THF gave the desired alcohol **8** in 73% isolated yield. Now the methylation of alcohol **8** with methyl iodide in presence of NaH as base in dry acetonitrile did not produce any trace of the desired product rather it gave the

Scheme 3

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Scheme 4

ring opened product **9** in 78% yield. Changing the base from NaH to K_2CO_3 provide the similar result. Reaction of **8** with methyl iodide in presence of K_2CO_3 in THF gave compound **9** in 61% yield. Using 1 equivalent of methyl iodide gave the ring opened N-methylated benzyl alcohol derivative. Although, 4-(N,N-dimethylamino)benzyl alcohol is successfully methylated to corresponding ether using methyl iodide in presence of base e.g. NaH. But in our case probably, the strain induced increase of nucleophilicity of aziridine nitrogen make it reactive towards methyl iodide. The vinyl group in aziridine ring makes it more strain and accordingly nucleophilicity of nitrogen increases¹¹.

Interestingly, Lukin *et al.* reported that reaction of anilines with 3-chloro-2-(chloromethyl)propene in presence of Na_2CO_3 gave vinyl-N-aryl aziridine, **12** however repeating this reaction using aniline always gave eight member dimer, **13** not even trace amount of desired compounds, such as **12** was found from crude reaction mixture (Scheme 5). The reaction using 4-methoxymethyl aniline also provide similar results. The reluctant to form four member ring and formation of dimer may be to avoid the ring strain. At this stage, we deemed it necessary to develop a new methodology that would to ob-

Scheme 5

tain compound **2** from compound **1** in single step.

When α -chloro ethers are treated with an alkyl organolithium compound, e.g. n-BuLi, hydrogen-lithium exchange may takes place to give carbinoid α -lithio- α -chloro ethers^{13,14}. α -Elimination of LiCl from these compounds then gives the corresponding alkoxy carbenes and these are very useful for [2+1] cycloaddition reaction of alkenes and alkynes to obtain cyclopropanes and cyclopropenes¹⁵. On the other hand, allylation of α -chloroethers can be achieved by trialkylallylstannane under conditions in which the halide is transformed into a carbon-centered radical¹⁶. Migita *et al.* reported that the reaction of aryl bromides with methoxymethyl tributyltin in the presence of a catalytic amount of dichloro bis(triphenyl phosphine) palladium was found to give arylmethyl methyl ethers¹⁷. Although the reaction is a novel aromatic methoxymethylation, but it suffer from many disadvantages including not easy to preparation of methoxymethyltin compounds which is toxic in nature, long reaction

Scheme 6

times, use of toxic solvent (HMPA) etc.

We have developed a methodology for methoxymethylation and benzyloxymethylation of aryl lithium generated from corresponding aryl bromides through the reaction with n-BuLi at low temperature. The reaction of aryl bromide **1** with n-

BuLi at -78°C for one hour and followed by quenching with methoxymethyl chloride (MOM-Cl) gave the methoxymethyl substituted product **2** in 76% isolated yield (Scheme 6).

After successful preparation of compound **2**, to test the generality of our approach we have applied our method into

Table 1. Methoxymethylation and benzyloxymethylation of aryl bromides^a

1. n-BuLi
2. MOM-Cl
or
BOM-Cl
-78 °C, 1 h

R = CH₃
or
R = CH₂Ph

Entry	Aryl Bromide	α -Chloroether	Product	Yield (%) ^b
1		MOM-Cl		76
2		MOM-Cl		72
3		MOM-Cl		81
4		MOM-Cl		71
5		MOM-Cl		64
6		BOM-Cl		72
7		BOM-Cl		76
8		BOM-Cl		84
9		BOM-Cl		67

^aReactions were run in THF with 1 mmol aryl bromide, 1.2 mmol n-BuLi and 1.1 mmol MOM-Cl or BOM-Cl. ^bIsolated yield.

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Scheme 7

some readily available aryl bromides to obtain the corresponding methoxymethyl- and benzyloxymethyl ethers. It has been found from Table 1, bromobenzene, 4-methoxybromobenzene, even *ortho*-substituted 2-methoxybromobenzene react nicely to obtain the corresponding methoxymethyl and benzyloxymethyl ethers in good yields. 4-Chlorobromobenzene also reacts with MOM-Cl and BOM-Cl in this conditions and produce 71% and 67% of desired products respectively. The electron deficient 4-nitrobromobenzene also react in our method and gave the expected product in 64% yield (entry 5, Table 1). Thus in our methodology, the carboxylation, reduction and alkylation, three steps were reduced to single step.

Although the functional groups those are not tolerable in presence of *n*-BuLi or aryl lithium (generated *in situ* under reaction conditions) are not applicable in this method. To resolve this problem, we are currently working on palladium catalyzed cross-coupling of aryl bromide with alpha-alkoxy acetic acid or alpha-benzyloxy acetic acid which will provide alkoxymethyl or benzoxymethyl ether after cross-coupling followed by decarboxylation (Scheme 7). The initial results are very much impressive and details will be published very soon. All the products in Table 1 are known compounds and the NMR spectra of all the products are perfectly matched with literature reports.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we have successfully synthesize our required compound **2**, which is not possible using traditional three steps methods and proves the generality of this methodology for methoxymethylation and benzyloxymethylation of both sterically and electronically diverse aryl bromides. The one-pot high yielding procedure hopes to be useful for synthetic community. Future work in this area will entail extension of this chemistry to a large substrate scope and will be published elsewhere.

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Supporting information

NMR spectra of some new compounds.

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